

Further Studies on *Salvia Coccinea* Linn

K. S. MUKHERJEE and P. K. GHOSH
Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati University,
Santiniketan, West Bengal.

Manuscript received 21 January 1978, revised 26 April 1978,
accepted 23 May 1978

IN a previous communication¹, we reported the isolation of a minor triterpene, m. p. 210-12° from the petroleum ether (60-80°) extract of *Salvia coccinea* Linn. (Fam: Labiate). On further investigation in petroleum ether (60-80°) extract of *S. coccinea* Linn, yields another triterpene-B (0.005%), m.p. 232-34° along with triterpene-A m.p. 210-12°. The triterpene-A crystallises from benzene-petroleum ether mixture, m.p. 210-12°, the elemental analysis of which indicates the molecular formula, C₃₀H₄₈O₂ (M⁺, 440). It imparts yellow colour with tetranitromethane and responds positive to Libermann-Burchardt test for triterpene. Its IR spectrum showed bands at $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3390 (broad, hydroxyl), 1649 (unsaturation) and 885 cm⁻¹ (exocyclic methylene).

That the triterpene-A contains an exocyclic methylene is evident from the NMR spectrum (a doublet of two protons in the regions 4.55 and 4.76 δ) and also from the ozonolysis of the acetate of triterpene which affords formaldehyde, characterized as its dinitrophenylhydrazone.

The NMR spectrum of the triterpene-A in addition to the presence of an exocyclic methylene also shows peaks at δ 0.75-1.60 (methyl and methylene protons), around 3.52 δ (dd, 2H, J=10 Hz, -CH₂OH) and a broad multiplet for one proton centered at 5.15 δ for a vinylic proton. The mass fragmentation pattern of the compound is typical of Δ^{12} -ursene type of triterpene². The mass spectrum of the triterpene-A exhibits peaks at m/e 440 (M⁺), 409 (M⁺-CH₂OH) 232 (retro Diels-Alder fragmentation), 207 (M⁺-232 H), 201 (232-CH₂OH), 189 (double hydrogen transfer from retro Diels-Alder fragment to form a highly conjugated allylic cation or 207-H₂O) and a peak at m/e 133 (201-C₈H₈).

In conformity with the Δ^{12} -ursene skeleton, triterpene-A acetate on catalytic hydrogenation in glacial acetic acid with Adams catalyst afforded a product which on repeated chromatographies gave uvaol diacetate^{3,4}, m.p. 156-158° as one of the products. This diacetate on hydrolysis with 6% ethanolic KOH, furnished a compound, C₃₀H₅₀O₂ (M⁺ 442), m.p. 230-32° identified as uvaol^{3,4} (II) by m.m.p. determination, Co-I. R. and Co-T. L. C. with the authentic specimen of uvaol.

All the above data show that the triterpene-A is dehydrouvaol (I), the location of exocyclic methylene at C₂₀ is being ascertained from the pronounced loss of 68 mass units (C₈H₈) from the fragment ion at m/e 201, giving rise to an intense peak at m/e 133

in the mass spectrum because the presence of exocyclic methylene at C₂₀ presumably facilitates the double allylic cleavage² in the ring E.

Triterpene-B, m.p. 232-34° was found to have molecular formula, C₃₀H₅₀O₂ (M⁺ 442). Its mass spectrum exhibits peaks at m/e 411, 234, 207, 203, 189 besides the molecular ion peak at m/e 442. It forms a diacetate, m.p. 156-58° and was found to be identical with dihydro derivative of triterpene-A [M uvaol (II)] by m.m.p. determination, Co-T.L.C. and Co-I.R. with authentic sample of uvaol.

The chloroform and alcoholic extracts of *Salvia coccinea* on chromatography over Brockmann alumina in the usual way afforded only β -sitosterol.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express their sincere thanks to Dr. M. M. Dhar of C. D. R.I., Lucknow, Dr. D. V. Ramana of I. I. T., Madras and Prof. (Mrs.) A. Chatterjee, University College of Science, Calcutta for spectral analysis. Thanks are also due to Dr. B. C. Das of Institut de chimie des substances naturelles, Gif-sur-yvette, France for mass spectrum of triterpene-B. One of the authors (P.K.G.) is also thankful to C. S. I. R., New Delhi, for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

References

1. K. S. MUKHERJEE and P. K. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1978, 55, 292.
2. H. BUDZIKIEWICZ, J. M. WILSON and C. DIERASSI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 3688.
3. LATE SIR JOHN SIMONSEN and W. C. J. ROSS, "The Terpenes", Cambridge University Press, 1957, Vol. IV, Chap. II, P.168.
4. K. HUZII and S. OSUMI, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1939, 59, 142.

Coumarins from the umbels of *Prangos pabularia* Lind

SUSHMA SOOD, B. D. GUPTA, S. K. BANERJEE* and P. R. RAO
Regional Research Laboratory (CSIR), Jammu-Tawi-180 001

Manuscript received 10 January 1978, revised 18 May 1978,
accepted 7 May 1978

PRANGOS pabularia Lindl. (Umbelliferae) is very rich in coumarins¹. The roots and fruits are reported for their medicinal value¹. The plant grows